

Viscosity of Electrolytes in Dioxane + Water Mixtures

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The B-coefficient of the Jones-Dole equation for twelve electrolytes in (10, 20 and 30%) dioxane+water mixtures at 30, 35, 40 and 45° have been calculated. From the B values, the effective rigid molar volume, its change with % of dioxane and temperature and the ion-solvent interaction have been inferred.

ION-SOLVENT interaction studies have been a subject of interest for the last two decades¹. The inference regarding the interaction is derived either from viscosity or from molar volume or from conductance studies or from a combination of such studies. Literature is full of such studies in pure solvents, but investigations in mixed solvents are scanty. In the present communication, the viscosity results obtained from KCl, KBr, KNO₃, KBrO₃, KIO₃, K₂SO₄, NaCl, NaBr, NaNO₃, NaBrO₃, NaIO₃ and Na₂SO₄ at 10, 20 and 30 mass fractions of dioxane at 30, 35, 40 and 45° have been analysed in terms of ion-solvent interaction. An attempt has also been made to find a relation between the B-coefficient and \bar{V}_e , the effective rigid molar volume.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the salts and dioxane used were of E. Merck 'Extra Pure' varieties. The preparation of the solutions etc and measurements were the same as described earlier². The time of flow did not exceed 0.2 sec in 20 minutes and density readings were precise up to 0.0002 gm. ml⁻¹. The concentration range was from 0.1 to 0.001 mol. l⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The results have been analysed in terms of the Jones-Dole equation¹ as the plot of $\eta_r - 1/C^{1/2}$ vs $C^{1/2}$ is linear. The intercept and slope of the plot give respectively the coefficients of A and B of which the constant 'A' is a measure of ion-ion interaction and the constant B is a manifestation of ion-solvent interaction (Table 1).

Dependence of B on temperature : According to Stokes and Mill³, the viscosity of a very dilute electrolytic solution incorporates that of the solvent plus the contribution from other sources. They are η^E , the positive increase due to the shape and size of an ion ; η^A due to increase in alignment or orientation of the polar molecules by the ionic field and η^D , the decrease in the viscosity arising due to the distortion of the solvent structure by the ions. Therefore, B-coefficients can be discussed in terms of these viscosity effects at different temperatures.

The B-coefficient of all salts increases (excepting Br⁻) with the increase in temperature. This indicates that the viscosity decrease due to solvent

TABLE 1—B/l. mol⁻¹

Mass fraction of dioxane	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%
<i>Salt</i>				<i>Salt</i>		
<i>KCl</i>				<i>NaCl</i>		
30	0.019	0.034	0.048	0.081	0.100	0.155
35	0.020	0.040	0.052	0.091	0.112	0.166
40	0.033	0.050	0.061	0.140	0.150	0.200
45	0.035	0.053	0.059	0.150	0.162	0.220
<i>KBr</i>				<i>NaBr</i>		
30	0.028	0.047	0.051	0.097	0.120	0.151
35	0.031	0.051	0.062	0.115	0.124	0.170
40	0.022	0.062	0.058	0.066	0.112	0.145
45	0.021	0.051	0.056	0.065	0.108	0.137
<i>KNO₃</i>				<i>NaNO₃</i>		
30	0.011	0.032	0.042	0.071	0.096	0.130
35	0.015	0.039	0.050	0.085	0.109	0.142
40	0.018	0.043	0.057	0.102	0.115	0.153
45	0.019	0.047	0.061	0.112	0.125	0.160
<i>KBrO₃</i>				<i>NaBrO₃</i>		
30	0.030	0.042	0.062	0.065	0.089	0.104
35	0.043	0.059	0.078	0.089	0.109	0.119
40	0.058	0.076	0.098	0.104	0.122	0.134
45	0.074	0.092	0.114	0.122	0.138	0.146
<i>KIO₃</i>				<i>NaIO₃</i>		
30	0.120	0.145	0.165	0.181	0.212	0.252
35	0.152	0.164	0.175	0.210	0.235	0.265
40	0.165	0.185	0.220	0.235	0.255	0.281
45	0.185	0.204	0.245	0.263	0.273	0.295
<i>K₂SO₄</i>				<i>Na₂SO₄</i>		
30	0.248	0.275	0.348	0.262	0.291	0.385
35	0.280	0.300	0.280	0.300	0.325	0.410
40	0.305	0.330	0.415	0.330	0.352	0.438
45	0.330	0.358	0.434	0.360	0.378	0.448

structure, i.e., η^D is small and hence $\eta^E + \eta^A > \eta^D$ and B is positive. The B value is found to be of the order at 30 and 35°

Hence, it can be concluded that the ion-solvent interaction is of the reverse order, i.e.,

Further, also according to Stokes and Mill³, the lesser the value of $\frac{dB}{dI}$, the greater is the ion-solvent interaction. The $\frac{dB}{dT}$ is found to be of the order :

which is in confirmity of our above conclusion.

Dependence of B on dioxane content: Mc Rae⁴ has suggested that the dioxane molecule has two non-adjacent dipolar group whose moments cancel, so that the effective reaction field is probably greater than is indicated by microscopic properties. Hence the frozen layer as suggested by Frank and Evans⁵ around the ion is expected to be constituted of both the water and dioxane molecules, possibly consisting more of the former than the latter kind of molecules; whereas, the diffused layer would consist of loosely oriented water and dioxane molecules, the extent of orientation decreasing with the distance from the ion till the outermost layer has the same structure and composition as that of the solvent. When the dioxane content of the solvent increases more dioxane molecule takes part in constituting the diffused layer and thus promoting a sort of ordering effect in the solvation sphere and hence would lead to larger values of η^E and η^A and exhibit an increase in the value of B with increase in dioxane content (Table 1).

Effective rigid molar volume: Fuoss and Co-workers^{6,7} from apparent molar volume and density data have confirmed Einstein's⁸ equation:

$$B = 2.5\bar{V}$$

where \bar{V} is the molar volume of the solute particles. Breslau and Miller⁹ designate this \bar{V} as the effective rigid molar volume, V_e . This V_e has been strictly defined as the volume which a mole of solute particles occupies when considered, from purely hydrodynamic reasons, as rigid microscopic spheres. The B-coefficient, from Table 1 has been utilised to calculate V_e^{10} for all the salts. The value of V_e , then obtained are recorded in Table 2 at 40° only for illustration.

The plot of B vs V_e is found to be linear and the equations that fit the data (both graphically and by least square methods) are tabulated in Table 3. This indicates that the slope of the plot of B vs V_e changes slightly with the change in the dielectric constant and also with the temperatures. The value of V_e decreases with the decrease in dioxane content of the solvent. This may be attributed to terms of

the hydrogen bond between water and dioxane molecules. As dioxane content is decreased more and more hydrogen bonded dioxane molecules are formed resulting in an increase in V_e .

TABLE 2— $V_e/1.\text{mol}^{-1}$ (AT 40° ONLY)

Mass fraction of dioxane	10%			20%			30%		
	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%
KCl	0.016	0.024	0.028	NaCl	0.038	0.072	0.098		
KBr	0.010	0.028	0.026	NaBr	0.033	0.052	0.071		
KNO ₃	0.003	0.019	0.026	NaNO ₃	0.049	0.053	0.074		
KBrO ₃	0.026	0.034	0.046	NaBrO ₃	0.052	0.058	0.034		
KIO ₃	0.080	0.081	0.102	NaIO ₃	0.111	0.121	0.126		
K ₂ SO ₄	0.147	0.161	0.204	Na ₂ SO ₄	0.156	0.167	0.211		

TABLE 3—RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN B AND V_e

Temp. (°C)	Wt. % of Dioxane	Relation
30	10	$B = 1.96\bar{V} - 0.004$
	20	$B = 1.92\bar{V} + 0.004$
	30	$B = 1.90\bar{V} + 0.006$
35	10	$B = 2.0\bar{V} - 0.004$
	20	$B = 1.96\bar{V} + 0.004$
	30	$B = 1.95\bar{V} + 0.003$
40	10	$B = 2.08\bar{V} - 0.002$
	20	$B = 1.90\bar{V} + 0.004$
	30	$B = 2.00\bar{V} + 0.006$
45	10	$B = 2.10\bar{V} - 0.004$
	20	$B = 2.08\bar{V} + 0.004$
	30	$B = 2.04\bar{V} + 0.006$

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